

RESOLUTE
Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

Project number 777372

**WP1 – Generation of
 reagents and cell lines to
 allow system-wide study of
 the SLC family**

D1.1 Vector generation

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¹ Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

R = Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc.

Dissemination level	PU ²
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Description of Work	Version	Date
	V0.4	28 Jun 2019

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	13 Jun 2019	First Draft (GW)
V0.2	14 Jun 2019	Comments and edits (AIP, TW)
V0.3	14 Jun 2019	Finished draft for review (GW)
V0.4	28 Jun 2019	Final Version

² Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web;

CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement;

CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Publishable Summary

RESOLUTE aims to unlock the therapeutic potential of solute carriers (SLCs) in a systematic and coordinated effort. To reach this goal, loss- and gain-of-function studies using SLC knock-out (KO) and overexpression (OE) cell models are crucial. In order to create these cell lines, a collection of KO and OE vectors was designed and generated by WP1. As detailed in the project proposal, a lentiviral CRISPR vector that expresses both the gRNA and the Cas9 protein was chosen to genetically delete >80% of the target SLCs. This vector allows stable integration of gRNA and Cas9 by selection with an antibiotic resistance marker that is encoded on the vector. Lentiviral gRNA vectors have been successfully generated for all of the 426 originally proposed SLCs. Additionally, gRNA vectors for another 20 SLCs, which have been classified as SLCs only after the project proposal was submitted, have been generated. To re-express the endogenously deleted SLCs in KO cell lines, two expression systems were selected: The HEK293 R4 Jump-In system that allows site-directed integration and inducible expression in HEK293 cells and a modified inducible lentiviral vector that stably integrates into the genome in a mainly random manner. For the purpose of RESOLUTE, vectors for both systems have been modified to allow expression of Human Influenza Hemagglutinin epitope (HA) and Twin-Strep® (Strp) tagged SLCs. To allow fast and efficient cloning of all 426 SLCs into these and other expression vectors, codon-optimized versions of the canonical SLC cDNAs were synthesized and inserted into gateway-compatible cloning vectors. To this date, all 426 proposed SLCs have been successfully cloned into a modified HEK293 R4 Jump-In vector and 419 out of 426 (98%) SLC cDNAs have been cloned into a modified lentiviral vector. All cloned plasmids were confirmed by Sanger sequencing and bacterial stocks were frozen to allow sustainable storage and rapid re-preparation of the vectors.

Methods

Lentiviral SLC CRISPR KO vectors:

CRISPR sgRNA sequences were designed for 446 target SLCs. The gRNA sequences were ordered as complementary single-stranded DNA oligos, which, after annealing, contained the 20 nt gRNA sequence and flanking overhangs for cloning into the BsmBI-digested pLentiCRISPRv2 vector.

Gateway-compatible SLC vectors:

Codon-optimized SLC cDNA sequences without STOP codons were synthesized and cloned into gateway-compatible pDONR221 vectors. To avoid editing of the overexpressed transgene in cells in which the endogenous SLC was deleted by CRISPR KO, it was ensured that the gRNA target site is not fully present in the codon-optimized sequences. Subsequently, STOP codons were added by insertional mutagenesis at the 3' end of the coding regions. These steps were performed by a commercial provider for gene synthesis who delivered a total of 852 plasmids (426 SLCs with and without STOP codon) to CeMM where the coding regions were cloned into expression vectors for two different cell systems, as described below:

Jump-In compatible expression vectors:

To express SLCs in HEK293 R4 Jump-In cells, HA-Strp tags were inserted into the pJTI™ R4 CMV-TO MCS pA vector, either upstream or downstream of the gateway cloning site to allow expression of N- or C-terminally tagged SLCs. SLC coding regions (without STOP codons) were then cloned into the C-terminally tagged expression vector using the gateway cloning system.

Lentiviral expression vectors for RESOLUTE cell lines:

To express SLCs in RESOLUTE cell lines, two gateway-compatible destination vectors were constructed by modifying the pLIX_401 vector (Addgene accession: 41393): The puromycin resistance gene was replaced with a blasticidin resistance and HA-Strp tags were inserted either upstream or downstream of the gateway insertion site. This resulted in two destination vectors that allow inducible expression of N- or C-terminally tagged SLCs in stably transduced and selected cells. To this date, 419 of the 426 originally proposed target SLCs (98%) have been cloned into the C-terminally tagged expression vector using gateway cloning (without STOP codons). Expression vectors for N-terminally tagged SLCs will only be generated if expression upon induction of the C-terminally tagged versions cannot be detected in western blots and immunofluorescence experiments.

Discussion

The originally proposed Flp-In system for SLC overexpression in HEK293 cells was replaced with the Jump-In system, the latest generation of this site-directed insertion and expression system. It has been shown and confirmed in our pilot experiments that the Jump-In system allows a tighter control of induced expression and more homogenous transgene expression levels in stably transfected cells.

Conclusion

The aim to clone a plasmid collection that allows to genetically delete and overexpress >80% of the proposed 426 SLCs in different cell line models has been reached.

Repository for reagents

The gateway-compatible entry vectors containing the untagged cDNAs (without STOP codons) for all 446 SLCs will be deposited at Addgene (<https://www.addgene.org/>), a non-profit organization who will distribute these plasmids to the research community against a small fee to cover their operating costs.